

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE PLATES AND SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

Since composite materials are increasingly used in the construction of light-weight structures, it is important to develop an analysis and design capability for a variety of loading situations. This capability is particularly important for low and medium impact energy situations where damage is difficult to detect and if undetected can result in catastrophic failure during service. In the present work, a finite element code which simultaneously models impact and progressive damage is presented. The impact process is modelled using a Hertzian-based contact law. Material failure is simulated using a progressive damage model and is implemented using a collapse load approach. Each mode of failure in the composite is based on a characteristic failure criterion. Comparison with experimental results shows that the finite element model predicts flexural response and damage, but is limited in predicting local contact stress effects.

INTRODUCTION

The performance level of a structural component is determined by its weight, stiffness, and strength. The increased use of composite materials in structural applications requires a better understanding of the static and dynamic damage characteristics of composites. A variety of numerical techniques have been used to study and predict the behaviour of composite laminates subjected to impact [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. The purpose of this research is to combine a progressive composite-damage model with an impact analysis to examine damage progression and its effect on the impact response of laminated composite plates.

INDENTATION LAW

Hertzian contact theory gives a force-deformation relationship between two elastic bodies in contact. The theory was developed for isotropic materials for static contact problems. Goldsmith [6] applied the Hertzian contact law to the impact between two colliding isotropic bodies, while Greszczuk [1] extended the theory to collision between an isotropic sphere and an orthotropic plate. Yang and Sun [7], and Sun and Tan [8] examined the indentation law experimentally and verified its use for dynamic modelling of impact. They modified the indentation law to account for unloading and permanent indentation. Furthermore, Tan and Sun [8] validated the Hertzian contact law for impact problems and found that numerical predictions agreed very well with experimental results.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The derivation of a finite element model for impact is governed by certain behavioural characteristics of the impact process. Previous numerical analysis have shown [5, 9, 4] that high local stresses in the vicinity of the impactor occur at the onset of impact and often initiate damage in the specimen; this suggests that a dynamic analysis is necessary. Three-dimensional finite element analysis of impact events shows that in the case of low- and medium-energy impact, transverse normal stresses [10, 2] are small, which implies that plate/shell analyses are appropriate. Furthermore, it has been shown [9] that at the onset of impact, transverse shear stresses are high due to the large local curvatures. These stresses often responsible for the initiation of damage and therefore must be included in an analysis. Based on these observations, a dynamic Reissner-Mindlin formulation for plate deformation was adopted. An implicit scheme was used for temporal integration.

The finite element used involves a bicubic-isoparametric plate element having 16 nodes with 5 degrees of freedom per node giving a total of 80 degrees of freedom per element. Second order strain-displacement relations are implemented in a tangent stiffness formulation for nonlinear analyses. The Hilber-Hughes- α implicit time-integration method was used to enhance numerical stability for this non-linear dynamic problem [11].

PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE MODEL

For isotropic, homogeneous materials such as metals, yield and post-yield theories are well documented and experimentally verified. On the other hand, for composite laminates, the analyst must make explicit assumptions regarding fibre-matrix interaction during the failure process. In a comprehensive review of failure and post-failure theories, Nahas [12] reports that there are at least 30 failure theories and 12 post-failure theories for composite laminates.

Unlike metals, composite materials have distinct mechanisms of failure. In the theory of elastoplasticity, the material is assumed to yield and lose stiffness; slip planes and dislocations occur and the material is said to undergo plastic flow. Composite materials tend to fail in distinct modes such as matrix cracking, fibre breakage, fibre buckling or delamination. This means it is necessary to treat each failure mode independently and

derive a separate criterion for each failure type. In collapse load analysis [13], a characteristic criterion is associated with each mechanism of failure. The mode of failure is "active" when it is the first criterion to be satisfied. This approach has advantages for composites as any number of failure mechanisms can be assumed for lamina or laminates provided a failure criterion is expressible in terms of stress or strain.

There are two components to a progressive damage model within a finite element analysis. Firstly, the failure criterion must be chosen; then this criterion is compared to the stress (strain) state to determine whether failure has occurred. The modal failure criterion proposed by Hashin [14] was used in the current analysis because it specifies distinct failure criteria for different lamina failure modes. Secondly, once failure has occurred, a post-failure model is applied to determine how the lamina is degraded by the damage. A post-failure theory where the stress is set to zero upon failure was adopted because it is the most conservative assumption and requires no empirical parameters for modelling energy release.

When evaluating the element stiffness matrix, the material constitutive matrix is calculated at the Gauss points during numerical integration. In the progressive damage model, stress and strain are evaluated at the Gauss points in each lamina and the failure criteria is applied. If failure occurs, the material constitutive matrix is modified previous to evaluation of a damaged element-stiffness-matrix. This procedure allows damage to occur locally within an element and thus gives a finer resolution of the damage zone. Failure progression may either be in a lamina or through the laminate. The current approach is also advantageous in that the failure criterion is evaluated at element location where the stresses and strains are most accurate.

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

A Rheometrics drop-weight impact rig was used for the experiments as reported in Houde [15]. The apparatus consisted of a 76.2 mm diameter ring to clamp the sample, a 3.74 kg, 12.7 mm dart equipped with a force transducer, a spring loaded drop tower which was capable of simulating much larger drop heights, a dart catcher to prevent bouncing, as well as a data acquisition system and control system interfaced with an IBM personal computer. Eight-ply, $[0, +45, -45, 90]_s$ quasi-isotropic samples of Hercules IM7/8551-7 graphite/epoxy, were impacted at 0.8 m/s.

Figures 1 and 2 show X-ray radiography and C-Scan results for a graphite/epoxy sample. While the C-Scan shows delamination damage, the X-ray radiography reveals matrix cracking. Through-thickness delamination locations were the consistent using either measurement technique. However, the C-Scan results show more damage in the 0° ply direction, indicating delamination propagation without cracking.

The experiment presented above was modelled using this developed finite-element code. The material stiffness and failure properties used are given in Table 1 as reported by Tennyson and Elliot [16]. Because cubic plate elements were used for the analysis, seven finite elements were used to model a quarter of the plate with a total of 1580 degrees of freedom for the entire plate. A flexurally clamped with inplane slip boundary condition was used ($w = \psi_x = \psi_y = 0$) on the outer boundaries, while quarter symmetry conditions $u = \psi_x = 0$ on $x = 0$, and $v = \psi_y = 0$ on $y = 0$. The mesh discretization and element numbering are presented in Figure 3. A comparison of the calculated contact force versus the experimental measured result is shown in Figure 4 for a portion of the experiment duration and as may be seen the numerical predictions compare well with the experimental data. The oscillations in the calculations are

Figure 1: X-ray radiography of graphite/epoxy after impact at 0.8 m/s (based on experimental data collected from Houde [15])

Figure 2: C-Scan of graphite/epoxy after impact at 0.8 m/s (based on experimental data collected from Houde [15])

Material	E_{11}	E_{22}	G_{12}, G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ρ
IM7/8551 Gr/Ep	164.0	8.30	2.10	2.10	0.34	1600
X_t	= 2.41 GPa		X_c = 1.04 GPa			
Y_t	= 73 MPa		Y_c = 173 MPa			
S	= 183 MPa					

Table 1: Properties of graphite/epoxy used for this analysis. All stiffnesses reported in GPa; all mass densities reported in kg/m^3 (obtained from Tennyson and Elliot).

Figure 3: Quarter-symmetry circular mesh used for dynamic analysis.

thought to result from high frequency vibrations of the plate and may result from the characteristics of the cubic elements and the relative mass of the impactor to the plate ($m_{impactor}/m_{plate} = 530$). It should be mentioned that these oscillations may also be real as their frequency was beyond the limit of the data acquisition system.

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the damage extent with modal strength for the top and bottom plies. Figures 2 and 1 give the corresponding C-Scan and X-ray radiograph of the corresponding experimental result. The difference in orientation of the damage zone shown in the radiography results is likely due to the symmetry assumptions made in the numerical analysis. The elliptical damage zone with a total area of 120 mm^2 was comparable to 140 mm^2 obtained from a C-Scan of the specimen.

CONCLUSIONS

The finite element model developed for this analysis is capable of modelling non-linear dynamic response of composite plates and shells subjected to impact loads. The cubic, isoparametric Reissner/Mindlin shell element has capability of predicting accurate displacement, stress and strain fields, which are critical for modelling damage. The model

Figure 4: Comparison of contact force results for a quasi-isotropic GRE plate under impact (experimental analysis reported in Houde [15])

Figure 5: Modal strength values indicating damage in the bottom ply

Figure 6: Modal strength values indicating damage in the top ply

handles geometric, material, as well as indentation non-linearities under dynamic conditions. To this end, the Tangent Stiffness method has been modified to account for displacement-dependent force as well as stiffness non-linearities. The model has been illustrated to accurately predict the dynamic response and damage of composite plates under impact.

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